

Acute Encephalitis Syndrome: A Study of Awareness in Rural Setting

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Abstract

The disease has been clinically diagnosed in India for the first time in 1955 in Tamil Nadu. Acute encephalitis defined as the acute onset of fever and a change in mental status (including symptoms such as confusion, disorientation, coma or inability to talk), and new onset of seizures (excluding simple febrile seizures). It is clearly pressing the public health emergency in India. It is a communicable disease so; information of cause plays important role to the prevention of this disease. This study aims to analysis the role of community participation to control the AES and level of awareness among the effected people of this disease. Community participation is more important in the rural environment, so we are trying to evaluate the role of this. We are trying to evaluate the level of awareness on the basis of some variables namely sources of knowledge, availability of vaccine's, participation of community, government institution and NGO's.

Keywords

Acute Encephalitis Syndrome, Community Participation, Awareness, Rural Settings, Communicable Disease.

Introduction

Acute encephalitis is a disease of fever and affected the mental status with the symptoms such as confusion, disorientation, coma or inability to talk and excluding simple febrile seizures. AES is cause of mortality and neuro disability in adults and children. This disease is clearly challenging the public health system of India. Between 2008 and 2014, there have been more than 44,000 cases reported and nearly 6000 deaths from encephalitis in India, particularly in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. In 2016 over 125 children reported to die in a Gorakhpur hospital alone. This disease have high case-fatality rate (CFR), and occurs as seasonal disease every year. The impact of this disease has been mainly on children below 15 year of age. Viruses of the disease have been mainly spread through fungus, bacteria, and parasites other toxins. The patients often present with acute onset of fever and altered consciousness, with a rapidly deteriorating clinical course, death within hours. Many of those who survive may have residual disability impacting on long-term quality of life. While Japanese encephalitis virus (JEV) is the leading diagnosed cause of acute encephalitis, other causes include enter viruses, scrub typhus, measles and other viruses circulating in the local area. In many cases, however, no etiological agent is determined, and such cases are categorized broadly as acute encephalitis syndrome.

The disease was clinically diagnosed in a state of southern India, Tamil Nadu in 1955. This disease has affected the 171 districts in 19 States. During 2016, 11,651 case and 1301 deaths were reported to the National Vector Borne Diseases Control Programme (NVBDCP), with a CFR of around 11 percent. Most deaths reported in Uttar Pradesh, followed by West Bengal, Assam and Bihar. The affected people by this disease have been belongs to the lower strata of the society. So we are trying to know that efforts done by government and NGOs, is enough or not to prevention by this disease.

Area of Study

The present study has been conducted at five blocks namely Aurai, Bandra, Baruraj, Bachaua, Dhali of Muzaffarpur District, Bihar. This study of illness behaviour in encephalitis also known as Chamki fever, these five Blocks of Muzaffarpur is specially

effected by Chamki (AES). These Block are just around five kilometres in radius of District Headquarter of Muzaffarpur.

Objective of study

Following work has been conducted with the aim-

To assess the level of awareness and community participation to control and prevention of AES.

Review of Literature

MalyaDev, Dutta (1991) state that the doctors and paramedical workers of India must go out to the community with one aim that is to educate the people. Khinchi, Y.R., Kumar, A. & Yadav, S. (2010) discussed the profile of children admitted in hospitals and trying to find the outcomes. R. Parthasarathy and R. Mubarak, Ali (1991) studied that the enhancement of the quality of life undertaken in various programmes.

Methodology

The data for the present study have been collected from 100 respondents for the required fulfilment of the information. The data have been collected through the observation and structured interview-schedule. The respondents have been selected by using the purposive random sampling. This study is quantitative and qualitative in nature. Data have been classified with the help of simple statistical and various tables. Secondary data has been collected through the research paper, articles and various resources.

Result and Discussion

Various variables have been chosen to evaluate the awareness about AES namely knowledge about sources of spread AES, heard about AES before affected, knowledge of vaccine availability etc. Data has been presented following on the basis of variables.

Heard about AES before affected- Out of 100 respondents, 8% of the respondents heard about AES, and 92% of the respondents not heard about AES before affected.

Sources of Spread of AES- 8% of the respondents know about sources of spread of AES, and 92% of the respondent not knows about sources of spread of AES before affected.

Knowledge of Vaccine Availability- out of 100 respondents, 1% of the respondents know about Vaccine Availability for AES, and 99% of the respondents not know about Vaccine Availability for AES.

Sources of Knowledge- 35% of the respondent heard by TV/Radio, 40% of the respondent heard by nearby people, 19% of the respondent heard by health worker, 6% of the respondents heard by other sources about the AES.

Role of Community Participation- Role of community participation play an important role for preventable to any disease. 69% of the respondent except for the role, and 21% of the respondents don't accept the role and 10 % of the respondents not sure about the role of community participation.

Vaccinated of AES after Birth- Vaccinated of AES after birth is important to secure the child by the disease. 2% of the respondent vaccinated of AES, and 78% of the respondent not vaccinated of AES, 20% of the respondents don't know about the AES vaccine.

Campaign by NGO and Government Worker- NGO and Government worker aware the people about AES by campaign but our data present only 2% of the respondent accepted for the campaign and 98% of the respondent denied for any campaign by the NGO and Government worker.

Condition of Child after Vaccinate- The conditions of child after vaccinate by AES is shown the effectiveness of the vaccine on the disease and children. 93% of the respondent accepts the effectiveness of vaccine and 7% of these respondents denied to effectiveness the vaccine.

Conclusion

The level of awareness between beneficiaries and community participation to control AES is plays an important role because it controls the disease in various manner. Availability of healthy food, good living environment and good quality of drinking water can be reduce the impact of AES. These all can be arrange through the help of community participation and NGOs. As per data we can see that the government is disabling to reach the people for awareness if disease. The number of campaign is very less for targeting population. it can be a reason that people are dying till now by this disease.

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